

Community-Based Disaster Management Planning and Hazard Risk Assessment for Social Security: A Case Study of Talla Johar Valley of Uttarakhand, India

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ABSTRACT: Participatory research approaches are increasingly admired by academic researchers and development institutions, facilitating change in partnership with local communities. The present paper deals with the concept of Community-Based Disaster Management (CBDM) and explain the impacts and community's perception regarding different hazards. In the present paper, researchers tried to demonstrate an approach to identifying and assessing threats in Uttarakhand's Talla Johar valley. The prime focus of this paper is on flooding, landslide, soil erosion, and forest fire, etc. This paper assesses hazard risks with local participation and compile the understanding of various disaster attributes based on risk assessment.

Keywords: Community-based Disaster Management, Community Participation, Hazard, Hazard Assessment, Management Assessment, PRA tools, Risk assessment, Vulnerability Assessment.

I. Introduction:

Over the past two to three decades, the economic losses and the number of people who have been affected by natural disasters have increased more rapidly. The recent catastrophe of Uttarakhand is the burning example of human, ecology and economic loss. To reduce the damages caused by disasters the government and international community's including donor agencies have taken various efforts. But due to lack of participation, most of the time community may not be prepared to face the disaster and this issue is prime of concern. White's (1945) work was one of the first detailed investigations about the human responses to natural hazards and led to the 'dominant' paradigm. 'The 'dominant' paradigm attempted to incorporate the human element of risk by focusing on people's perception of environmental hazards and how they dealt with them' (Gaillard et al. 2007). The concerned authority (Government, non-government and international organizations) implement various plans before and after the disasters. Most of them are very successful during the

project period but gradually weaken as the year's pass. We should know that without sustainability, disaster management efforts will not preserve. The most common community involvement elements are partnership, participation, empowerment and ownership by the local people (Maskrey, 2011). The emphasis of disaster management efforts should focus on the local communities. Unless the disaster management efforts will not start at individual and community level, it is difficult to reduce the loss and impact of the calamity. There needs to be community participation during the initial programming stage of disaster management activities. Being at the forefront, communities should have the capacity to respond to threats on their own. Communities should be involved in managing the risks that may harm them. While different communities empowerment programs related to disaster mitigation have achieved their objectives, they are often short term, and sustainability issues in these efforts are rarely addressed (Kafle and Murshed, 2006). As the primary stakeholder and recipient of the direct impact of disasters, the community has hardly been given a chance to participate in decision-making and implementation activities. Communities become vulnerable when it has left alone limited resources to cope with disasters. It has been experienced by the locals that generally small and medium scale disasters occur more frequently than large-scale disasters. Participatory techniques are one way of ensuring communities participation in planning strategies to mitigate them. It has been increasingly advocated that population directly affected by environmental hazards should be involved in decision making and development of policies (Wisner et al. 2004). Community empowerment demands their participation in risk assessment, mitigation planning, capacity building, participation in implementation, and development of the system for monitoring, which ensures their stake.

Community-Based Disaster Management (CBDM)

The Community based Disaster Management (CBDM) approach promotes harmony between bottom-up and top-down move to address the challenges and difficulties. To be effective implementation local communities must be supported into analyzing their hazardous conditions, vulnerabilities, and capacities as they perceives

themselves(Pandey and Okazaki, 2005). The CBDM approach initially provides opportunities for the local community to evaluate their level of vulnerabilities based on their own experiences. The CBDM system acknowledges that a considerable number of stakeholders should be involved in the management process, so that capacities and transfer of resources may be possible (Pandey. Et.al., 2016).

Number of published literature based on CBDM highlighted some facts on increasing sustainability:

- ▶ The "culture of coping with the catastrophe" and " culture of disaster risk reduction" exist.
- ▶ Community and supporting agencies involve in motivation, cooperation and sustainable ownership of resources
- ▶ The risk assessment process involves the real participation of all sectors and age groups in capacity building.
- ▶ Wider stakeholder's entanglement and effecient use of physical, economic and technological assets to reduce hazards and vulnerability.

II. Objectives of the Study:

The major objectives of this study are -

1. To identify the natural constraints and its impacts in the study area
2. To conduct the Hazard Risk Assessment with the help of local respondents in the Talla Johar Valley.

III. Methodology:

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. For the study, six villages of Talla Johar valley have been found as most vulnerable in terms of disaster risks. Twenty-five respondents from the each village have been selected. Thus a total of 150 samples has been taken for data collection. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) tools have been also used to check the ground reality. Focused group discussions and interviews have been conducted to understand the responses of local communities. Hazard Vulnerability Index has been prepared for measuring hazard, vulnerability, and management assessment separately to elucidate the risk assessment by giving them ranking based on local responses. The local community's perceptions regarding

different aspects of sustainability and hazard occurrences and management have been gathered through a pre-structured questionnaire (Pandey. Et. al. 2016). Secondary data has been used to analyze and explain the geographical information of the study area with other additional information. Socio-economic, household, population and land use data have been gathered from District Census Hand Book.

IV. Study Area:

Talla Johar Valley is located in northern India adjacent to Tibet and Nepal; the Johar Valley is a remote area within the Pithoragarh district of the western Kumaon region of Uttarakhand, India Eastern Ramganga river or Goriganga river (Figure 1). The valley used to be a major trade route with Tibet. The best-known villages in the valley are Munsiri, Milam Tejam, Nachani, Rasiabagar, and Bhaiskhaal, and these villages come under Munsiri Tehsil. The central Gori valley from Munsairy to Milam is known as Johar. The Johar valley is also divided into two-part 'Talla Johar valley' and 'Malla Johar valley.'

Source: Map Constructed in ArcGIS

Figure. 1 Map of the study Area 'Talla Johar' of Kumaon Region

The Johar Valley ranges in altitude from 2,290 mts. At Munsiyari to 3,872 mts. in Milam. The upper Johar Valley constitutes part of the eastern border of the Nanda Devi Biosphere Reserve buffer zone. For study here, we have taken lower Johar Valley (Pandey., Et.al., 2016). It lies between the middle Himalaya and lower Shiwalik, between 29° 16' 10" N to 29° 24' 11" N latitudes and 79° 41' 21" to 79° 48' 13" E longitudes. The Johar Valley's mountainous landscape includes river valleys and alpine meadows, with alpine glaciers in the distance. As described by the International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD), these rangelands are incredibly fragile and critical ecosystems that support livestock and accommodate essential watershed functions and provide valuable and biologically diverse resources.

Drainage

The valley's major river is the Goriganga, which starts at the Milam glacier and flows southeast, fed by other glaciers and streams from the Nanda Devi Biosphere reserve to the east and Panchachuli Peaks to the west. The river Kaliganga system drains the area. The Milam glacier is a receding glacier and moves backward at a fast rate; the newly formed Moraine belt is the perfect area to study plants' origin from the adjacent mountains and Bugyals. The valley is located in the middle of the Kumaon region (Pandey., Et. al., 2016).

Geology

The geology of the area is divided into three significant zones (i) zone of ridges and steep slope (ii) moderate zone (iii) zone of minimum elevation.

The zone of ridges and steep slope includes a significant north portion of the river. It lies at an altitudinal zone of more than 2000 mts. It was thus subjected to high erosion. It covers 45per cent area of the total area of the basin (Pandey et. al., 2016).

The moderate slope zone lies between 1200 to 2000 mts; thus, erosion is also comparatively less. This zone involves maximum anthropogenic interference, thus contributes to full silt discharge to the principal stream. The soil is enriched with silt, and therefore it is potentially fertile, covering roughly 20 percent area of the river basin (Table 1). The valley covered with mountain soils in general, are immature and have a thin surface layer. They are therefore very prone to erosion and loss of fertility. Deforestation, disused terraces, and road-building activities have encouraged landslides along the mountain slopes. This has led to acute soil erosion problems in the middle Himalayas.

Table 1: Major Types of Soil found in Pithoragarh District, Uttarakhand

S.N.	Situation	Altitude m	Soil type
1.	Irrigated Lower Hills	600-1200	Alluvial Sand
2.	Rainfed	600-1200	Residual Sandy
3.	Mid Hill South Aspect	1200-1700	Sandy Soil
4.	Mid Hill North Aspect	1200-1700	Brown Forest Soil
5.	High Hill	1700-2500	Red to Dark Black Loam
6	Very High Hill	2500-3500	Red to Dark Black Loam, Black Meadow Soil Type
7.	Alpine Pastures	>3500	Heavy Textured Meadow Coarse Textured

Source: Negi, 1993

Climate:

The climate valley describes a "tundra" variety where the mild summer season is followed by a freezing and snowy winter season. The amount of precipitation is high towards north and west in thickly forested areas. During the coldest months of December and January, the tropical and temperate mountain ridges and high land receive snowfall and have a minimum of - 4 to -5 temperature °C and a maximum of 38 °C. The temperature rises from mid-March through mid-June. Regions lying at 3,000 to 3,500 meters (9,800 to 11,500 ft) become snow covered for four to six months. At location like the river gorges at Dharchula, Jhulaghat, Ghat, and Sera of district Pithoragarh, temperatures reach 40 °C (104 °F). The annual average rainfall is 1200 mm., winter is a time for transhumance, the seasonal migration of the Bhotiya tribe with their herds of livestock to lower, warmer areas. The topography varies from glaciated peaks to grassy plateaus and rangelands to river valleys fed by the glaciers, snowmelt, and monsoon rains (Pandey., Et. al., 2016).

Vegetation:

In Talla Johar Patti, the bugyals extend from the Tibetan border town to the Goriganga Valley as far as its junction with the Ralam Valley. The shadow valleys or grooves are often forested with *Betula-utilise*, associated with the shrubby alpine vegetation and some sporophytic undergrowths. All these plants are rich in medicinal content. Beyond Milam, the sub-alpine vegetation is represented by yellow-flowered *Berberis sp.*, white-flowered *Rosa*, *Ribes grossularia*, species of *Juniperus*, *Lonicera*, and *Ephedra gerardiana* (Pandey., et. al., 2016).

Village Profile of the selected Villages:

Among the selected villages of Talla Johar valley village Nachani has the highest population (Table 2). The principal livestock are buffalos, cows, bulls, goats, hens, and dogs. The villagers' main occupation is agriculture, and other disciplines are poultry farming, dairy farming, and bee-keeping. The most pressing problem of the village is the lack of a motorable road. Although the plan was sanctioned 15 years ago, which is yet to be materialize. Another infrastructural loophole is in the area of health. The villagers have to either go to the central Pithoragarh city for even the mildest of illnesses. In emergency cases, such as labor pain or sudden health deterioration, trekking down on foot for 10 km is the only way out (Pandey., Et. al., 2016). The 108 emergency service holds no good for these people because neither the vehicle can come to the village (on account of the absence of road) nor can it keep standing in the area for long for it also has to cater elsewhere. Electricity supply does not pose a grave problem unless a pole or wire gets damaged. Almost all existing families have cattle. Those who do not own cattle buy milk from others. Fuel-wood and grasses are brought from the nearby forest.

People are dependent on their farms for food as also PDS to get access to rice and wheat. Manure is organic (cow dung only), Rajma, lobhia, soybean (locally called *bhat*), *tur daal* are grown but are destroyed by the monkeys and the wild pigs. There is no monoculture in crops. Mixed farming with cow dung as manure used. In fruits, *malta*, gooseberries, lemon, and oranges are grown. There are virtually no government schemes operating in the village. The village seemed to suffer significantly from the lack of a motorable road and hospital. Even a post office or post-box was seen missing. Motorable roads, a health center with a permanent ASHA, and a post-office are the primary needs that should be addressed on an urgent note (Pandey., Et. al., 2016).

Table 2: Village Profile of the Selected Villages of Talla Johar Valley

Name of the village	Number of families	Total population			Population Livestock
		M	F	Total	
Tejam	151	280	263	543	388
Rasiabagar	16	31	32	63	45
Bhaiskhal	40	124	149	273	198
Nachani	235	526	512	1038	488
Timtiya	49	91	120	211	98
Dhekuna	48	137	141	278	210

Source: Based on Primary Survey

V. Result and Discussion :

Hazard Identification in the Talla Johar Valley

The Johar Valley climate is influenced by the summer monsoon and cold air masses in winter and westerly storms, which may bring heavy snowfall. The area is fall under extreme snowfall and blizzard conditions throughout the year and at higher elevations. The summer monsoon brings intense rainfall (>1000 mm) to the valley. The area has been subject to extreme meteorological/hydrological events such as floods, landslides, snow avalanches, and earthquakes. Owing to its typical geomorphic setting, high relief variation, the dominant impact of monsoon winds, presence of glaciers and glacial lakes, thick forest cover, along the higher reaches, the area is vulnerable to various natural types of hazards. Annually the damages caused to life and property by cloudbursts, flash floods, forest fires, landslides, and mass movement processes in the valley are enormous. The studies show that the Johar Valley is prone to seasonal flash floods, which lead to massive damage to property and loss of life occasionally. The flash flood in the Johar Valley is related to the extreme rainfall and occasional cloudburst events during the monsoon period from mid-July to mid-September. Cloudbursts usually occur in the upper catchments of the tributary valleys. The impact of the cloudbursts is seen in the central Talla Johar valley, which recorded a quick high discharge and caused a consequential loss of property and even life. Forest fire is a matter of great concern to the people and the local administration. Periodic forest fires also increase soil erosion in the Johar Valley. Massive alluvial fans, terraces, etc., confined to the valley bottom, and the mass movement are apparent (Pandey., Et. al., 2016).

Community Perception over Different Aspects of Hazards :

Knowledge of naturally occurring processes that may pose a hazard to life and property in mountain environments is held by long-standing and indigenous inhabitants of such areas. Their local or indigenous knowledge has influenced land use and resource management decisions and adaptive strategies for generations. Their indigenous knowledge and expertise provide a rich corpus of information to scientists, engineers, planners, and outsiders involved in development projects in a particular area. Hazards are caused due to changes in geophysical setup. The scale of severity is based on the state of fragility and vulnerability. So far as the frequency of hazards in the Talla Johar Valley is concerned. The trend (frequencies) has been

categorized under six heads namely (i) Increasing rapidly (ii) increasing slowly, (iii) constant, (iv) reducing rapidly, (v) reducing gradually, and (vi) don't know (Pandey., et. al., 2016). The respondents have regarded the landslide's hazards, floods, cloudburst, forest fire, heavy rainstorm, and soil erosion as increasing rapidly by 77, 83, 81, 90,73 and 60 percent. Eighteen percent of the respondents perceived that heavy rainstorm and soil erosion related cases have been increasing slowly. Less than 5 percent of the respondents perceived that they have no idea about changing trend of hazards in their area.

Perceptions Regarding Causes of Hazards

Intensive household level attitudes were collected for particular hazards: their root cause and other responsible factors were identified through the questionnaire. Slope cutting, heavy rainfall, overgrazing and deforestation, were identified as the driving factors causing these hazards.

Table 3: Local's Perceptions regarding the cause of Hazards

Causes	Hazards											
	Landslides		Floods		Cloudburst		Forest Fire		Heavy Rain Storm		Soil Erosion	
	Res*	percent	Res*	percent	Res*	percent	Res*	percent	Res*	percent	Res*	percent
Deforestation	150	100.00	150	100.00	120	80.00	150	100	16	10.67	150	100
Slope cutting and construction of Roads	150	100.00	130	86.67	0	00.00	60	100	0	00.00	150	100
Improper Draining on slopes	120	80.00	90	60.00	20	13.33	0	00.00	15	10.00	130	86.67
Heavy Snowfall	18	18.00	10	06.67	0	00.00	0	00.00	10	06.67	10	06.67
Overgrazing	10	06.67	5	03.33	0	00.00	100	66.67	0	00.00	123	82.00

Steep Slopes	60	40.0 0	0	00.00	10	06.67	0	00.00	20	13.3 3	76	50.67
Heavy Rainfall	130	86.6 7	150	100.0	150	100.0	0	00.00	145	96.6 7	150	100
Changing Land Uses	55	36.6 7	22	14.67	30	20.00	90	60.00	0	00.0 0	58	38.67
Faulty Agricultural Practices	40	26.6 7	15	10.00	05	03.33	10	06.67	0	00.0 0	27	18.00
Glacial lake Outburst	55	36.6 7	20	13.33	12	08.0 0	0	00.00	0	00.0 0	14	36.67
Tourism	10	06.6 7	10	06.67	0	00.0 0	15	10.00	10	6.67	20	13.33

Source: Primary Survey, 2013

* Res. - Number of respondents, Based on Community Response

The improper draining on the slope also found as an important factor. Most of the respondents think heavy rainfall and deforestation as an important factor for cloudburst. Overgrazing, deforestation, and land use change are the major factors responsible for forest fire in the area. Primarily human activities like slope cutting, road construction, deforestation, improper draining on the slope, are responsible for soil erosion of about 150, 150,130, and 150 respondents. 130, 150, and 120 respondents identify the slope cutting and construction of roads heavy rain, and improper drainage over slope were identified as major responsible factors for landslide hazards.

About 150 respondents recognized faulty heavy rainfall, deforestation, slope cutting, and road construction are a tool for soil erosion in the area (Table 3). For the forest fire hazard deforestation was considered the foremost factor by respondent; beside, Slope cutting and overgrazing also considered as a major factor for forest fire.

Disaster Risk Assessment

The vulnerability assessment identifies what elements are at risk and the causes of their vulnerable conditions. The result of the disaster risk assessment is a ranking of the community's disaster risks as the basis of planning for risk reduction (Pandey., Et. al., 2016). Through hazard assessment, the likelihood of the occurrence, the severity, and duration of various threats are determined. At the local level, the most important factor concerning the vulnerability is the level of income that determine the types of houses. Poor quality of houses adds the exposure of the local people to disasters. Stone made and mudmade houses and roofs made of galvanized tins and thatch grass are more vulnerable than the RCC houses. Usually, places under municipal areas

are better protected, because, most of them made of cement concrete. Poverty status, education, communication and transportation systems, accessibility of public resources such as forest produce, government facilities, drinking water, and presence of agricultural banks/credit banks, NGOs, and other service delivery institutions can be used to assess vulnerabilities in an area.

Hazard Assessment

The average frequency, effect, and ranking of flood hazard in Rasiabagarh and Baiskhal are 3, followed by Tejam 2.7 and Nachani 2.7. These villages are highly vulnerable to landslide. Forest fire hazard registers 2.7 and 2.3 respectively in Tejam and Baiskhal villages. Where as village Timtiya (2.7) effected by heavy rainfall (Table 5). Thus it can be seen that the probability of flood and landslide disaster in the first four villages is widespread and intense. In comparison, the landslide is a very frequent disaster in all the five villages except Timtiya along in Talla Johar Valley.

Vulnerability Assessment

In Rasiabagar and Baiskhal, the vulnerability of floods hazard on infrastructure, resource, population, and the economy is 2.32, which is the highest among the selected villages. These villages shows highest frequency of flood hazard as well as forest fire hazard 1.95 and 1.77, respectively. Timtiya village found less vulnerable in terms of hazards. The recorded ranking value is the lowest among the selected villages. Most hazard-prone villages are Baiskhal and Rasiabagar. In Rasiabagar village, the vulnerability of floods and landslides hazard is 2.8. Village Tejam is most prone to forest fire, the ranking value is 2.4, which is the highest among the selected villages. In village Dekuna, an identified significant hazard is heavy rainfall with its ranking value is 1.8 (Table 6).

Assessment of Hazard Management

The assessment of hazard management table 7 shows that most people opted for prevention and mitigation strategies before the occurrences of disasters to weaken the impact of the disaster. The weather forecasting and warning before and after an event is essential in the case of heavy rainfall. Local people want the government to

set up a weather station in every village for alert before the onset of heavy precipitation, which is responsible for several water-induced disasters. In the case of Nachani village most of the respondent stated that after occurrence of forest fire government give compensation and does safekeeping and replantation in the affected area. Local people believe that NGOs and other institutions are not actively participated during and after hazards.

Risk Assessment

The risk assessment over the study area of various disasters shows risks of the landslide in Rasiabagar, Bhaiskhal, and Dekuna are 5.0, 5.02, and 3.90 respectively. While of flood risk in village Rasiabagar is 5.0, Bhaiskhal is 4.70 and Timtiya is 3.10. Risk assessment of forest fire in Tejam, bhaiskhal, and Rasiabagar is 3.90, 3.11, and 1.90 respectively and heavy rainfall (3.20) in Timtiya. Thus Table 8 shows the risk of landslide and flood is very high in all six villages in Talla Johar Valley.

Table 5: Hazard Assessment Table

Name of Village	Name of Disaster	Hazard										Average		
		Frequency			Effect			Ranking						
		Definite	Chance	No Chance	High	Medium	Low	High	Medium	Low				
Tejam	Flood,	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	8/3=2.7
	landslide	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	6/3=2
	Forest fire	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	8/3=2.7
Rasiabagar	Flood,	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	9/3=3
	landslide	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	9/3=3
	Forest fire	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	5/3=1.7
Bhaishkhaal	Flood,	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	9/3=3
	landslide	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	9/3=3
	Forest fire	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	7/3=2.3
Nachani	Flood,	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	8/3=2.7
	landslide	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	7/3=2.3
	Forest fire	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	5/3=1.7
Timtiya	Flood	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	8/3=2.7
	Forest fire	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	5/3=1.7
	Heavy rainfall	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	8/3=2.7
Dekuna	Land Slide	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	9/3=3
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	4/3=1.3
	Heavy rainfall	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	6/3=2

Source: Primary Survey, 2013
*Ranking Based on community Responses

Table 6: Vulnerability Assessment

Name of Village	Disaster	Population			Building			Infrastructure			Resources			Economy			Average
		H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
Tejam	Flood,	-	2	-	3	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	12/5 =2.4
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	2	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	12/5=2.4
Rasiabagar	Flood,	-	2	-	-	-	3	-	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	14/5=2.8
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	-	3	-	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	14/5=2.8
	Forest fire	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
Bhaishkhaal	Flood,	3	-	-	-	2	-	3	-	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	14/5=2.8
	Landslide	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	14/5=2.8
	Forest fire	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
Nachani	Flood,	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	6/5=1.2
	Forest fire	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
Timtiya	Flood	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8
	Forest fire	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	7/5=1.4
	Heavy rainfall	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	-	8/5=1.6
Dekuna	Land Slide	-	2	-	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	13/5=2.6
	Forest fire	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	7/5=1.4
	Heavy rainfall	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	9/5=1.8

Source: Primary Survey, 2013

*Ranking Based on community Responses

Table 7: (A) Management Assessment

Name of Village	Disaster	Level of Awareness : Government and Community			Effect of Regulation for Disaster			Reaction of Government :After Disaster Occurs			Forecasting: Effective Level by Government		
		H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L
Tejam	Flood,	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Landslide	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Forest fire	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
Rasiabagar	Flood	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Landslide	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
Bhaishkhaal	Flood,	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Landslide	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1
Nachani	Flood,	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	-	1
Timtiya	Flood	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
	Forest fire	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1
	Heavy rainfall	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1
Dekuna	Land Slide	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	1
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1
	Heavy rainfall	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1

(B) Management Assessment Table---

Name of Village	Disaster	Level of Warning: Before Occurring Disaster			Prevention & Mitigation of Disaster			Level Participl Ation: of Community Disaster Management			Level Of Participation: of Non-Government In Disaster Management			Level of Participation: Government In Disaster Management			Average
		H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	H	M	L	
Tejam	Flood,	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	16/9=1.6
	Landslide	-	-	1	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	17/9=1.7
	Forest fire	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	15/9=1.5
Rasiabagar	Flood,	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	2	-	15/9=1.5	
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	15/9=1.5	
	Forest fire	-	-	-	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	14/9=1.4	
Bhuiskhal	Flood,	-	2	-	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	16/9=1.6	
	Landslide	-	2	-	-	-	1	3	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	15/9=1.5	
	Forest fire	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	12/9=1.2	
Nachani	Flood,	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	2	-	17/9=1.7	
	Landslide	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	2	-	-	14/9=1.4	
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	18/9=1.8	
Timiya	Flood	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	14/9=1.4	
	Forest fire	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	1	17/9=1.7	
	Heavy rainfall	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	12/9=1.2	
Dekuna	Land Slide	-	-	1	3	-	-	3	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	18/9=1.8	
	Forest fire	-	2	-	3	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	1	14/9=1.4	
	Heavy rainfall	3	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	11/9=1.1	

Source: Primary Survey, 2013(*Percentage Based on Multiple Responses)

RISK ASSESSMENT= HAZARD ASSESSMENT * VANURABILITY ASSESSMENT/ MANAGEMENT ASSESSMENT

Table 8: Risk Assessment Table

Name of Village	Disaster	Disaster Assessment	Hazard	Vulnerability Assessment	Management Assessment	Risk Assessment
Tejam	Flood		2.7	2.4	1.78	3.64
	Landslide		2	1.8	1.89	1.90
Rasiabagar	Forest fire		2.7	2.4	1.67	3.90
	Flood		3	2.8	1.67	5.00
	Landslide		3	2.8	1.67	5.00
Bhaishkhaal	Forest fire		1.7	1.8	1.56	1.90
	Flood		3	2.8	1.78	4.70
	Landslide		3	2.8	1.67	5.02
Nachani	Forest fire		2.3	1.8	1.33	3.11
	Flood		2.7	1.8	1.89	2.60
	Landslide		2.3	1.2	1.56	1.70
Timiya	Forest fire		1.7	1.8	2.00	1.53
	Flood		2.7	1.8	1.56	3.10
Dekuna	Forest fire		1.7	1.4	1.89	1.30
	Heavy rainfall		2.7	1.6	1.33	3.20
	Land Slide		3	2.6	2.00	3.90
	Forest fire		1.3	1.4	1.56	1.20
	Heavy rainfall		2	1.8	1.22	3.00

Source: Primary Survey, 2013

VI.Conclusion :

The Hazard risk Assessment analysis shows that the selected villages are under high risk of floods, landslides and soil erosion related problems. In the present research participatory approach has been effeciently applied in hazard risk assessment. The purpose of involving local community in hazard risk assessment is to widen their capacity of duologues with government and relevant stakeholders. The anthropogenic process or landuse changes like construction of roads on sensitive slopes, falulty agriculture practices, expansion of settlement zone over upslope areas, overgrazing, etc. have triggered the problem of frequent flooding, widespread land sliding and excessive soil erosion in the area. The study found that the role of the community is very signifnicant in mitigation and management of pre, during and post disasters. Although government and local organizations contributing to handle the problems at their level (reconstruction of the retaining walls to prevent the landslides), but it does not proven helpful to that extent due to lack of maintenance and mismanagement.

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